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**ROLE PLAY WORLD COMMUNITY:
EXPLORING THE ANONYMOUS SIDE OF THE INTERNET**

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the anonymous side of the Internet, specifically RPW, or what is known in the Philippines as “Role Play World” Role Play World, or RPW, exists in an anonymous setting where different identities can be created depending on the users’ preferences. This study aims to explore the experiences of RPW users in an RPW community based on anonymous online interactions. By interviewing five RPW users aged 16–18 who use RPW through in-depth interviews, the researchers identified many factors that influence users to use RPW and their different perspectives on using RPW. The results of this study strongly suggest that an online disinhibition effect exists in the RPW community, which means that people feel more comfortable saying things online that they would be hesitant to say in person because they can remain completely anonymous and invisible behind the digital screen.

Keywords: Anonymity, Role Play World, Online Disinhibition Effect

INTRODUCTION

In this modern era of technology, smartphones and computers are readily available for people of all ages to easily access the Internet for various purposes, such as shopping, gaming, gossiping, and entertainment. Social media platforms are frequently used by most people on the Internet as a medium for pleasure, leisure, passing time, and avoiding the present situation of trouble or pain (Subudhi et al., 2020). Teenagers are commonly observed in today's generations on social media platforms. As technology progresses, the degree to which users, particularly teenagers, interact online becomes increasingly widespread (Panek, Nardis, & Konrath, 2013). Teenagers use social media on a daily basis because they provide them with communication and information services, as well as an avenue for establishing new connections and maintaining existing ones (Botou & Maarsellos, 2018). Social media platforms, such as Facebook, have become a way for people to interact and communicate with each other. With different ways of communicating and interacting on social media, different groups or communities have been developed that attract different users to join depending on their interests. Furthermore, it was found that age is a significant factor in bond strength with an online group: young people, specifically teens, identify with online communities more strongly than older generations do (Näsi et al., 2011).

Social networking sites allow different groups or communities with common interests to thrive and develop (Sonia and David, 2011), and one of these online communities is RPW, or in the Philippines, "Role Play World". The Role Play World (RPW) is a community on social media platforms such as Facebook, where users can create their own character or identity and connect with other users through anonymous online interactions. In RPW, users frequently communicate using pseudonyms or anonymous identities, which allows them to maintain a level of anonymity when interacting online while discovering parts of themselves that may be difficult to express in their real-life interactions. This phenomenon

is called the online disinhibition effect, which can be described as when people behave differently online than they would in real life (Suler, 2004).

The significance of RPW communities lies in their ability to provide a space for users to engage in activities that are in line with their interests, while developing a sense of connection among RPW members. However, the anonymous nature of RPW communities poses both risks and challenges. Cyberbullying, harassment, and addiction are among the issues that can arise in online communities (Kuss and Griffiths 2017). Despite these challenges, the anonymous interactions that occur in the RPW community have been recognized by RPW users as a means of escaping from reality, allowing users to relieve stress and engage in creative expression. According to Keipi et al. (2015), various forms of anonymity are integral to online experiences, providing expressional benefits to young people. In addition, social networking sites such as facebook open an avenue to young people for bonding social capital through providing social and emotional support by way of peer interaction (Chew, LaRose, Steinfield, & Velasquez, 2011).

While some existing bodies of research study anonymous interactions on social media, they do not specifically study anonymous communities such as RPW. Therefore, this study aimed to explore the experiences of young RPW users who engage in anonymous interactions, focusing on the experiences and perceptions of RPW users. This study seeks to contribute to the understanding of anonymous communities, such as RPW, and their significance in the digital age. Moreover, we aimed to provide insights into the experiences of young RPW users and the impact of anonymous interactions on their well-being and social development.

METHODS

The study adopted a qualitative approach to obtain an in-depth understanding of RPW users' perceptions of using RPW, in which two sets of interviews were used. A phenomenological qualitative approach was also used by the researchers because this type of approach investigates the experiences and how the person interprets them (Luborsky & Lysack, 2011). The phenomenological approach allowed the participants to explain their experiences in the RPW community and, therefore, was the most appropriate approach for the particular research questions investigated in this study. The goal of this study is to examine RPW users' reasons for using RPW and their experiences in using them. Thus, purposive sampling was used to gather information from selected RPW users. Data collection for this study was conducted until all required interview consent forms were signed by the respondents and returned to the researcher. Five RPW users were selected to participate in this study, all of whom consented to participate. Two participants were from Binuangan, and the other three were from Balingasag. The two participants claimed to be RPW writers, and the other three claimed to be RPW users only. The participants were RPW users from 2017-2019 to and were still active up to this day. The researchers constructed 17 research questions to ensure that all necessary data will be obtained regarding their experiences and perceptions in interacting anonymously online through the RPW community. The first interview, which was checked by the instructor, was used to gather data from the selected RPW users. The first interview was conducted during the 2nd week of February and lasted for approximately 20-30 minutes. Another interview was conducted during the 3rd week of February, where a range of 5-9 questions was constructed. All these questions were developed based on the respondents' data during the

first interview. The interviews ranged in length from to 5-10 minutes, with an average of seven minutes. The interviews were conducted face-to-face, where they were tape-recorded and transcribed. Furthermore, Axial coding was used to identify the themes and subthemes of the respondents' corresponding answers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study revealed five primary themes with corresponding sub-themes, which include the following: the key features of RPW that the respondents like (sub-themes: hoods, online anonymity); the perceptions of RPW users towards RPW (sub-themes: escape from reality and entertainment); the behavior of RPW users inside RPW (sub-theme: personality); the roles of RPW users and the benefits that respondents get in the RPW community (sub-themes: self-esteem, writing skills, comfort).

Theme 1: The Key Features of RPW

Role Play World has features that attracted individuals to join its expanding community. There are several features that RPW possesses which encourage the users to keep participating in it. The following sub-themes are united to form Theme 1:

Online Anonymity

Anonymity is fundamentally important for the full exercise of the right to freedom of expression, as guaranteed by the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights). Thus, privacy rights and anonymity are intricately related. Therefore, anonymity is not just an act of hiding one's identity, but it is also an act of protecting your own privacy as a human being. The respondents strongly liked this feature in the RPW community because it provides them privacy and freedom.

Respondent #2: *“I really like being able to seek comfort with my RPW friends despite the fact that everything is anonymous.”*

Respondent #3: *“I like RPW because I can post everything I want without being judged by other people since the identities of users are anonymous.”*

Respondent #5: *“The feature that I liked in RPW is that the identity of the users are hidden.”*

The anonymous feature that the RPW community possesses is something that the respondents liked. All of them claimed that this feature enables them to gain benefits such as being able to find comfort and being able to post everything they want to post because no one will judge them at all. Furthermore, several studies have confirmed that online peer support groups have been found to give positive benefits like that of offline peer support groups. With this, the RPW community acts as an online support group and has a similar feature like peer support group interactions offline which have been able to offer support including: social connectedness, comfort, empowerment, and recovery processes (Williamson, et al., 2015., Naslun, et al., 2016 & Merry, et al., 2019).

Hoods

The RPW community consists of different users who have different interests, in return RPW users developed small groups or what is called in the RPW community as “Hoods”. Hoods in RPW consists of like-minded users who share a common interest, for example RPW users may be interested in writing, drawing, or even just acting or roleplaying as someone else (it may be a character online from k-dramas or anime shows that the RPW user is interested in). In order to fully express their interests, RPW users will try to join hoods. The following responses clearly indicate that the respondents liked this certain key feature in the RPW community.

Respondent #1: *“I really like the sister/brotherhood or writer hood in RPW. Since I am a writer in RPW, these hoods can improve my writing skills because the members of it will give*

examples and advice to me. Aside from that, the hoods are also a way for me to make new friends.”

Respondent #1: *“I communicate with my RPW friends through messenger. I also joined group chats of sisterhoods. I was able to meet a lot of new people in RPW.”*

Respondent #4: *“One feature that I like in RPW is the sis/bro hoods because the members always interact and communicate with me.”*

According to DICTIONARY.COM, the word “Hood” comes from a native English suffix denoting state, condition, character, nature, etc., or a body of persons of a particular character or class, formerly used in the formation of nouns: childhood; likelihood; knighthood; priesthood. The RPW users view hoods as a small group of people with the same interest as theirs. RPW users liked this certain key feature of the RPW community because it gives them a sense of belongingness to one of the RPW users who interact with them, having said that they have the same interests as theirs. According to Slavich & Cole (2013), a need to belong in order to form close bonds with others and to align with one's cultural and subcultural identities, and to feel a part of the communities around them appears to be deeply rooted in our biology, even down to the human genome. This may explain why the RPW community developed and created hoods or small groups because it strengthens the connections between RPW users who have a common interest.

Theme 2: The Perceptions of RPW Users

RPW users have different viewpoints in using RPW. According to Keipe, et al., (2014), anonymity is a complex phenomenon that can be approached from many perspectives. The participants had a variety of experiences that provided them with different perspectives on RPW. They shared to us different perspectives as to how they see RPW. The following three sub-themes combined to form Theme 2:

Escape from Reality

Many individuals have the tendency to believe that social media is not the answer to life's difficulties. However, the respondents claimed that social media, particularly RPW, played a role in helping them deal with their challenges in life.

Respondent #1: *“ For me, RPW is an escape from the real world. In RPW, no one will judge me as a person because they do not know me in real life. Because of the friendliness of other RPW users, RPW enables me to temporarily forget my problems in life.”*

Respondent #3: *“My life revolves around RPW and I consider it as an escape from reality. It allows me to truly express myself. I am comfortable expressing myself there because I am not worried of being judged since no one knows my real identity.”*

Respondent #5: *“I consider RPW as a place to escape reality because whenever I write stories there, I feel like I am able to temporarily forget my problems in life.”*

According to Jouhki, et., (2022) ,escapism represents relief-seeking that pushes people away from their daily problems and worries. Moreover, escapism has been identified as one of the key drivers behind online behaviors (Jarman, et al., 2021 & Liu, et at., 2022). RPW has provided the respondents a way to escape their problems temporarily. According to the respondents, these problems stem from external pressures such as relationships, financial worries, and other personal problems, or adverse events causing stress and anxiety. Thus, seeking help online might help RPW users to escape from their problems and ultimately the reality.

Entertainment Platform

There are many ways to entertain ourselves. Throughout history, there have been several types of entertainment, which have changed as a result of advancements in technology. In RPW, the respondents said that it offered them a variety of entertainment options which greatly contributed in terms of amusing themselves.

Respondent #2: *“RPW really provides me entertainment by enabling me to communicate with other people from other places. RPW users are nice strangers who can be trusted and who also do not judge, which may be the reason why I am comfortable in RPW.”*

Respondent #3: *“When I first started staying in RPW, it used to stress me out because I had met a lot of ignorant people with a toxic mindset. However, those experiences taught me something valuable about life which is kind of fun.”*

Respondent #4: *“I think that RPW is an entertainment platform where your identity is hidden. I made a lot of friends which means that I have a lot of people to talk to. Talking to RPW users’ around my age makes me comfortable.”*

Respondent #5: *“For me, RPW is a place where I can go whenever I want to have fun. It is where I can freely write my own wonderful stories that have attracted lots of supporters.”*

Social media users actively select social media that best fulfills their individual needs such as information, entertainment and socialization among others (Dzogbenuku, et al., 2022). RPW enabled the respondents to be entertained by being able to connect with friends and share their personal experiences towards each other. Furthermore, users not only access and exchange information but also find a place for the expression of the affective dimension, which is part of human nature (Serrano-Puche, 2020).

Theme 3: Behavior of RPW Users

When an individual is anonymous online, they may communicate more boldly than they would in a face-to-face situation (Clark-Gordon, et al., 2019). The respondents have exhibited different behaviors that they do not often exhibit in real life. Due to the anonymous setting of RPW, the respondents claimed that it allowed them to express their true selves. The respondents shared to us all of the things that had changed due to the anonymous interaction between other RPW users online.

Personality

All of the respondents claimed that their personalities in RPW were different from who they were in real life. They said that each time they logged into their respective RPW accounts, their personalities changed or that they behave differently in the RPW community.

Respondent #1: *“In RPW, I am jolly and friendly. However, in real life, I am jolly but not that friendly. I am shy in real life.”*

Respondent #2: *“My personality in real life and in RPW is far different. In reality, I am not talkative, but in RPW, I talk a lot.”*

Respondent #3: *“My personality in RPW is very different from who I am in real life. In RPW, I am not afraid to be really honest about how she truly feels, which is something I struggle with in reality.”*

Respondent #4: *“In RPW, I am talkative. However, in real life, I am not.”*

Respondent #5: *“To be honest, I am pretty shy in real life, but whenever I use my RPW account, I feel like my behavior has changed because I become talkative to other users.”*

Online anonymity allows individuals to present themselves more ambiguously and express themselves in different ways (Yan & Tan, 2012). The respondents have exhibited different behaviors that they do not often exhibit in real life. Moreover, the respondents stated that RPW's anonymous environment allowed them to freely express their true selves, which is something that they do not do in their real accounts.

Theme 4: The roles of RPW users

In contrast to the sub-theme; Hoods, the RPW community offers a lot of activities in which users engage in anonymously, for example: Writing stories, Playing Games, and Threads

which is an activity in RPW which pertains to writing or commenting in posts and continuing the conversation or topic like a string of words. With this, RPW users possess a specific role, sometimes RPW users may have two or more roles in the RPW community because of the multiple hoods that the user is in.

Respondent #1: “I am a writer in RPW and I post stories and post inspiring quotes as well as my rants in life.”

Respondents #3: “I am a gamer in RPW and I sometimes go live-play with my RPW friends. I am also a threader, I always do threads and I often meet new friends because of doing it.”

Respondent #4: “I only talk with my friends there and I also post my rants about life in RPW.”

Respondent #5: “I write dedication stories from either lovers or enemies. I am also a Genshin player and I sometimes play with other users.”

The roles that RPW members have, helped to keep them motivated to participate in the RPW community. One of the primary reasons for the RPW user to engage in the RPW community is the opportunity to assume different roles and personas. Furthermore, the RPW community provides a chance to users to express different personalities that might not be expressed in their daily lives.

Theme 5: The benefits of RPW

Role Play World has become an integral part of every RPW user’s lives, transforming how they communicate, share information, and connect with other people. RPW offers numerous benefits that can improve an individual’s social interaction and their personal growth. All of the participants have benefited in different ways from engaging themselves in RPW. They expressed to us the advantages of participating in the RPW community. The four sub-themes listed below were merged to form Theme 2:

Self-esteem

Self-esteem is an essential aspect of psychological health and has a significant impact on how we think, feel and act. In the modern world, social media platforms have become known as important sources of acceptance and self expression for many people. Those who actively engage in social media platforms particularly in RPW, tend to experience higher self-esteem due to the positive feedback and social support they receive from their online connections. Furthermore, research shows that people with high self-esteem were more likely to experience benefits such as a positive sense of well-being and as a result they were able to cope up with stress and anxiety. (Orth, et al., 2012). The respondents shared to us their experiences in RPW and how it helped them boost their self-esteem.

Respondent #1: *“Being an RPW user was the reason why I became confident in making and sharing my stories to other people.”*

Respondent #3: *“RPW is really beneficial because it enables you to not be shy and be confident. It is really helpful for me because it taught me how to be confident.”*

Respondent #5: *“Because of RPW, I realized that I had already adopted the confidence I had shown there, which, in my opinion, helped me gain confidence in real life.”*

During the developmental stage of adolescents between the age of 11-19 years old, youth undergoes the process of identity development, and during this stage self-esteem is an important part of this development. As cited from Burrows, (2017), Adolescents' self-esteem is likely to be affected by any feedback they read on social media platforms during this developmental stage. According to the respondents, the RPW community offers them support and feedback which develops their self-esteem and their confidence.

Socializing Skills

Socializing skills play a crucial role in our lives for it is the one that will enable us to establish connections and build relationships. In RPW, the opportunity to acquire and refine an individual's socializing skills is provided. The users have the ability to develop and practice their social skills through continuous involvement and interaction with other RPW users. This implies that individuals can improve their social skills while having fun connecting with others and also while maintaining a level of anonymity.

Respondent #3: *"RPW helped me improve my communication and socializing skills by teaching me how to approach and interact with strangers. It helped me in improving an aspect of myself with which I had previously struggled: how I control my emotions, and handle my problems well."*

Respondent #4: *"Talking and sharing so many things with the people I met in RPW helped me improve my socializing skills. I realized that because of RPW, I became better when it comes to communicating with other people."*

Respondent #5: *"To be honest, RPW helped me practice my social skills and express my emotions in such healthy ways."*

As American psychologist Robert J. Havighurst once said, "Socializing skills are not something we are born with; they are learned and developed throughout our lives" (Havighurst, n.d.). This statement mainly highlights the importance of developing and refining our socializing skills through continuous learning and practice. The respondents expressed to us their experiences in the RPW community in terms of improving their social skills, and we found out that it did in fact help them develop their own social skills. With this, the RPW community acts as a place for other RPW users to interact and improve their social skills.

Writing Skills

Writing is a vital and effective instrument for self-expression, communication, and knowledge preservation. Social media users' participation in sites like Facebook and Twitter has been found to increase their vocabulary and advance their writing abilities (Li, 2010; Yunus et al., 2012). In RPW, a Writer hood exists, which is composed of writers who have the same interest; to write stories. These authors have the ability to express themselves by writing and sharing on RPW as they hone and refine their writing abilities. The respondents expressed their love for writing in RPW and how it helped them develop their own writing skills.

Respondent #1: *“RPW always makes me feel better, especially one of my famous writer friends. She never forgets to react and give comments on how to improve my writing skills. The RPW users really helped me in improving the overall aspect of my writing skills.”*

Respondent #5: *“RPW played a role in helping me develop my strength in the field of writing.”*

Respondent #5: *“I kinda like RPW because it enabled me to improve my literary abilities.”*

In a study about using Facebook to help students with their writing, Abdulateef (cited in Alfaki and Alharthy, 2014) came to the conclusion that students were highly motivated to practice English writing informally because writing on Facebook allowed for freedom of expression, convenience of time, and the support of their peers' comments and feedback. Writing in the Role Play World community provides a unique opportunity for individuals to develop and shape their own stories. They are then able to learn through feedback from other users as well as the suggestions made by other RPW writers who are already experts in the field of writing.

Comfort

Role Play World is an online community where you can seek comfort. One advantage of utilizing RPW is being able to seek comfort from other users who are also using RP accounts. Even if users in the RPW community remain anonymous it is still not a hindrance for asking help or comfort. As cited from Weidman et al (2012), The social compensation hypothesis states that the internet primarily benefits individuals who feel uncomfortable communicating face-to-face. The responses given to us by the respondents indicate that they are uncomfortable communicating face-to-face especially when it comes to sensitive topics, such as mental health or family problems. Thus, in the RPW community, RPW users obtain comfort as a result of simply talking and interacting with other RPW users online. This can be also connected to the fact that RPW community provides peer support as discussed from the sub-theme; Online Anonymity.

RPW user #1: “Whenever I have problems in life, I have someone to talk to without being shy and I can also share everything I feel with my RPW friends since they do not know me personally. They are the ones who comforted me in my darkest times.”

Respondent #5: “RPW relieves my stress because I have my RPW friends to comfort me whenever I am encountering problems in life.”

Respondent #5: “RPW is a good help when you have problems because the users there are vocal, very friendly, easy to interact with, and socially active and give advice that is really comforting to hear.”

The respondents claim that the RPW community actually helps them obtain comfort by providing them with recommendations from their friends or peers in that group. Communities like RPW, which provides social and emotional support through peer contact from either their close internet friends or from the RPW community, offers young people a method to improve their connection, according to research by Chew et al. (Chew, et al., 2011). Moreover, the desire for acceptance in a group or society is fundamental to the motivation toward security and self-esteem, and as such, it is a primary objective for many

individuals who utilize the advantages provided by social networking sites (Näsi et al., 2011).

CONCLUSION

The results of this study strongly indicate the significance of anonymous interactions in the role play world community (RPW); users from the RPW community are then able to communicate and express themselves freely as they maintain a level of anonymity in their online interactions, meaning that their offline identities are kept hidden and anonymous. In relation to the results of this study, we found that RPW users expressed themselves differently depending on their interests and motives. With this, we also found that the online disinhibition effect (Suler, 2004) is in fact present in the RPW community, specifically among the RPW users we interviewed, this effect pertains to the different behaviors displayed by users in social media and in real life.

This study proved that anonymous online interactions can have a positive impact on users' communication, socializing, and writing skills. Thus, we further conclude that RPW is not just merely an entertainment platform where individuals interact with others anonymously; it is also a platform where one can express their own feelings and develop their own skills without being limited. With anonymity, limitations can be transcended, giving the freedom to express oneself, and it is also a platform where one can remain secure and anonymous.

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